

COREnext One Click Recap

11.12.2025 | corenext.eu

As COREnext approaches its conclusion, this newsletter offers a concise snapshot of the project's journey, bringing together highlights from events, publications and contributions made throughout its duration. Readers are invited to explore the full breadth of outputs in one place: visit the COREnext Zenodo platform for open-access materials, watch all project videos, and browse the deliverables section on the COREnext website.

It provides a straightforward way to revisit the work accomplished and to access the resources that will continue to support the community beyond the project's end.

COREnext Events

COREnext Partners Engage Worldwide: Insights from 62 Events Shaping Europe's Future

Connectivity Landscape

Across the full duration of COREnext, partners took part in **62 events**, ensuring a strong and sustained presence within the European and global research, industrial and policy landscape. This broad participation reflects the consortium's active commitment to dissemination, technical exchange and engagement with communities shaping future connectivity technologies.

[Read more](#)

COREnext Publications

COREnext Scientific Output: Key Publications Advancing Research in Connectivity, Computing and Sub- THz Technologies

Throughout the COREnext project, partners produced a substantial body of scientific work that reflects the breadth of research carried out across communications engineering, semiconductor design, embedded systems, security and computing architectures. In total, **37 scientific papers** were published, including conference papers, journal articles, a

poster abstract, a book chapter and a white paper. Together, they demonstrate both the depth and continuity of the project's scientific contributions.

[Read more](#)

[Subscribe To Our Newsletter](#)

COREnext Zenodo Community

[Discover the COREnext Collection on Zenodo](#)

The COREnext project has developed its dedicated collection on Zenodo, offering open access to publications, datasets, deliverables and other key outputs as they become available. The platform provides a reliable, long-term repository for the project's scientific and technical results, supporting transparency, reuse and wider dissemination across the research community. Partners, stakeholders and interested readers are invited to explore the collection and follow its updates as COREnext progresses.

[Read more](#)

COREnext Deliverables

All reports in one place - enjoy research results and innovations!

Welcome to the Public Deliverables section of **COREnext**, a European project dedicated to **research and innovation** in the fields of **5G, 6G, cyber security,** and **trustworthiness**. Here, we present the tangible outcomes of our rigorous **research and development** efforts, showcasing our commitment to advancing technology and ensuring a **secure digital environment**. Dive into our deliverables to explore the cutting-edge solutions and insights emerging from our collaborative endeavors. Join us on our journey towards shaping the future of connectivity and security in the digital era!

[Read more](#)

Watch Our Videos And Subscribe!

Funded by the European Union

25 videos!

SUBSCRIBE

CORENEXT
on **YouTube** channel!
@COREnext project

Subscribe!

Don't Miss Out On Our Demonstration Brochure!

TrustEvaluation and IoT Management demo

WINGS
ICT SOLUTIONS

The demo showcases how the Trust Manager evaluates IoT devices in real time using trust metrics, updating each device's trust index dynamically. Based on these values and resource availability, the Trust Manager Orchestrator assigns tasks to the most reliable and capable devices, ensuring secure and efficient operation.

CORE NEXT

The Trust Evaluation Function calculates a trust score (0 to 1) for each device class by normalising key metrics, applying weights based on importance, and adjusting for data age using exponential decay. This ensures recent data has greater influence, with the final score derived from a weighted average of the adjusted metrics.

EXPECTED RESULTS

- Calculated trust scores of devices
- A graph of trustworthiness vs number of tasks/workloads
- Evaluation of the execution time

WORKING TOWARDS END-TO-END TRUSTWORTHINESS

COREnext believes that trustworthiness needs to be a native part of 6G as anticipated applications will merge the digital and physical worlds.

The goal of the project is to strengthen the mobile communication ecosystem in Europe by addressing key challenges associated with beyond 5G use cases.

Activities stretch from radio hardware innovation to compute architectures – with trustworthiness in focus.

corenext.eu

@COREnext_EU
COREnext
COREnext project
@corenext.bsky.social

JOIN US

Funded by the European Union

European core technologies for the next generation - communication-computing hardware

CORE NEXT

Eavesdropper avoidance **imec**

This sub-THz demonstrator showcases how beam-steering technology can be used to enhance link security. The system focuses on preventing eavesdropping by dynamically controlling signal direction. It offers an interactive experience for users to engage directly with the beam-steering process.

The system integrates MATLAB baseband signal processing with analogue beam-steering transceivers, featuring four independent RF front-ends and antennas for real-time beam control. An interactive interface enables live visual monitoring and operation.

Beam-steering at sub-THz frequencies enhances link security by lowering interception risks. Real-time user interaction demonstrates practical beam control, improving public understanding of physical-layer security and offering a scalable solution for future high-frequency wireless networks.

The demo shows how real-time beam-steering at sub-THz frequencies enhances link security, offering hands-on insight into practical physical-layer cybersecurity for future networks.

RF Fingerprint for Wireless Network Security **ERICSSON**

The Radio Fingerprint demonstrator offers an interactive look at how AI can use subtle hardware impairments in radio devices to enhance cellular communication security. By learning these unique signatures, machine learning models can identify authorised transmitters and detect unauthorised access attempts.

The demo uses machine learning models trained on transmitter non-idealities to classify radio devices in real time. It employs real hardware to transmit authentication signals and identifies authorised devices based on physical signal characteristics, without decoding the data.

The system enables device identification using hardware-specific features, without cryptographic keys. It lowers the risk of unauthorised access from devices with identical chipsets and provides a low-complexity, efficient method to enhance physical-layer security.

The demonstration introduces RF fingerprinting and shows how machine learning can authenticate radio devices securely and efficiently. It highlights how physical-layer security can complement traditional cryptography to strengthen wireless network trustworthiness.

Secure Acceleration (FPGA) **NOKIA**

The Secure Acceleration demonstrator showcases FPGA-based hardware acceleration for improved digital platform efficiency. It allows multiple tenants to securely share resources, using cryptographic components and key exchange protocols to protect sensitive data, such as health information, during processing.

The FPGA acceleration board supports secure multi-tenant resource sharing, featuring cryptographic modules and secure key exchange protocols. It enables real-time, privacy-preserving data processing in sensitive areas such as healthcare.

High datarate interconnects over plastic fiber **infineon**

This demo is based on the concept of high speed data link for communication via PMF in the H-Band, and PMF coupler in package at H-Band.

- MMICs in eWLB package, assembled on PCB
- H-band PMF coupler realized in package
- H-band PMF fiber and holder

This is the first in-package PMF coupler demonstrated in the H-Band, offering a compact, low-loss, and cost-effective solution for high-speed data links. It enables faster communication with reduced energy consumption, supporting future applications such as next-generation data centres.

The goal of the demonstration is to prove the concept of communication via PMF in H-Band.

Trustworthy Computer Platform M³ **barkhausen institut**

M³, developed at Barkhausen Institut, is a modular and secure operating system built on a tiled hardware architecture. Each component runs on a separate, isolated tile, following a security-by-design approach that limits the impact of potential compromises. This architecture enhances containment of untrusted software and hardware, strengthening trust in connected systems.

The platform provides hardware-level isolation between processing components in heterogeneous systems, enabling secure execution environments that mitigate hardware-induced vulnerabilities. Its adaptable architecture supports diverse, multi-vendor system configurations.

The architecture enhances system resilience by containing faults within individual hardware modules and reducing the risk of system-wide compromise through trusted execution zones. It supports secure, scalable design essential for future digital infrastructure.

The objective of this demonstration is to illustrate how hardware isolation strengthens the trustworthiness of complex digital systems. The M³ platform demonstrates a practical method for securing next-generation platforms by compartmentalising potential risks at the hardware level.

The demonstrator enables efficient and secure hardware acceleration for multiple users or applications, ensuring data confidentiality with robust cryptographic protection. It illustrates scalable, secure resource management for future digital infrastructures.

The goal of the demonstration is to show how sensitive data can be securely processed within shared hardware environments. It highlights a crucial advancement towards secure, efficient computing for digital platforms requiring hardware acceleration in multi-tenant, high-security contexts.

[Explore our brochure where all 6 demonstrations are described!](#)

COREnext believes that trustworthiness needs to be a native part of 6G as anticipated applications will merge the digital and physical worlds. The goal of the project is to strengthen the mobile communication ecosystem in Europe by addressing key challenges associated with beyond 5G use cases. Activities stretch from radio hardware innovation to compute architectures – with trustworthiness in focus.

Download Our Trifold

CORENEXT

CORENEXT is an EU-funded initiative that will bring together expert stakeholders in future mobile networks and integrate their perspectives in key focus areas like digital, analogue, and integrated solutions for computing, communication, and sensing.

Funded by
the European Union

CORENEXT

www.corenext.eu / info@corenext.eu

This email was sent to {{ contact.EMAIL }}

You've received this email because you are registered with COREnext.

This document has been prepared by the COREnext project, which is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them.

[Cancel subscription](#)

